

ELEKTROPOEZDLARNING TEBRANISHINI RICHAG-DISKLI ISHQALANUVCHI SO'NDIRGICHLARI KONSTRUKTSIYASINI HISOB-KITOB MUSTAXKAMLIK USULLARINI YARATISH

Khromova Galina Alekseevna¹
Kamalov Ikram Saidakbarovich²,
Makhamadalieva Malika Alievna³

¹doctor tech. sciences, professor

²acting docent,

³doctoral student of the Department of "Electric rolling stock",
State Transport University, Uzbekistan, Tashkent
<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7947173>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 08th May 2023

Accepted: 16th May 2023

Online: 17th May 2023

KEY WORDS

*Elektr poezdi, tutqichli diskli
ishqalanish tebranish
amortizatorlari, tutqichli diskli
ishqalanish tebranish
damperlari qismlarining
ratsional o'lchamlari,
takomillashtirilgan hisoblash
usuli, algoritmi, dastur,
MATHCAD 15.*

ABSTRACT

*Maqolada elektr poyezdlari uchun tutqichli diskli
ishqalanish tebranish damperi konstruksiyasining
mustahkamligini hisoblashning yangi usuli keltirilgan.*

Temir yo'llarning harakatlanuvchi tarkibining tebranishlarini ishqalanuvchi juftiga qo'yiladigan asosiy talablar: ishqalanish koeffitsientining barqarorligi, juftlikning yiyilishya bardoshlilik past, materialning elastikligi va qattiqligining past moduli, issiqlik kengayishining past koeffitsienti, yaxshi ishlash - ishqalanish materialida, etarli mexanik quvvat, korroziyaga qarshi, yopishqoqlik, issiqlikka chidamlilik va boshqa ishqalanish xususiyatlari [1,2,3].

Ishqalanish tebranish so'ndirgichi ishqalanish beqarorligining asosiy omillari: ishqalanish elementlarini ishlab chiqarish texnologiyasini buzish (vulkanizatsiya, issiqlik bilan ishlov berish paytida harorat rejimiga mos kelmaslik); hatto belgilangan toleranslar doirasida ham alohida qismlarning o'lchamlari bo'yicha og'ishlar; ishqalanish koeffitsientining o'zgarishiga yuqori sezgirlik bilan nomukammal dizayn.

Ishqalanadigan tebranish so'ndirgichining nominal o'lchamlarini aniqlash, raqamli hisob-kitoblarni amalga oshirishdagi asosiy vazifadir. Elektropoyezdlari uchun xarakteristikalarining barqarorligi va richagni diskli ishqalanish tebranish so'ndirgichlarini ishlashi ishonchliligi, ishqalanish yuzasining yuklanish xususiyati bilan belgilanadi [2, 3]. Yuklanishni hisoblash ketma-ketligi va dastak-disk tebranish so'ndirgich nominal o'lchamlari algoritmda keltirilgan. Disk tipidagi gidrofriksion so'ndirgichlarning dinamik egilish

siljishlari, deformatsiyalari va kuchlanishlari bo'yicha raqamli tadqiqotlar algoritmi, sxemasi va metodikasi ER2 (ER-9E) elektropoyezdning ishqalanish amortizatori misolida bajarilgan [4,5,6].

O'zgaruvchan qattqlik va disk tipidagi gidrofriksion dampning massasi bo'lgan elastik val tebranishlarining dinamik modelini yaratish uchun biz quyidagi taxminlarni kiritamiz.

1. Diskli elastik valning modeliga tashqi diametri d_B bo'lgan aylanuvchi elastik qattiq tayoqcha kiradi, bu konsol Richaglab-quvvatlovchiga ega: val aylanuvchi aylanish tezligiga ega. ω_B . elastik novda qismlarining elastik egilish deformatsiyalari ikki tekislikdagi funktsiyalar bilan tavsiflanadi $YOZ - y_B(z,t)$ va $XOZ - x_B(z,t)$. Ushbu funktsiyalar bo'limlarni valning uzunligi bo'ylab joylashtirish koefitsientlari z va o'rganilgan tebranish jarayonlarining vaqti t va davomiyliqlik ishlari bilan taqqoslangan holda hisobga olinadi [4,5,6].

Disk tipidagi gidrofriksion dampning modeli asosida loyihalash sxemasi 1-rasmda ko'rsatilgan.

Harakatlanuvchi disklar bilan ulanish uchun valda pazlar qilingan. Bunday val konstruksiyasi bo'laklarning o'zgaruvchan egilish qattqligiga ega bo'lib, har bir soni z_n da o'zgarib turadigan funktsiya bilan xarakterlanadi, bu yerda $n=0 \div 3, l_{kn} \leq z_n \leq l_{kn+1}$.

$$I_B(z) = I_{0B} \left(1 + \sin \frac{\pi z}{L} \right) = I_{0B} + I_{0B} \cdot \sin \frac{\pi z}{L} , \quad (1)$$

bu yerda $J_{0B} = \frac{\pi d_B^4}{64}$ elastik valning inertsia momenti, m^4 .

1-rasm.- ER -2 elektropoyezdi (ER -9E) uchun RD tipidagi disk tebranish so'ngdirgichining hisobiy sxemasi RD tipidagi elektropoyezd tebranish ishqalanish so'ngdirgichi bo'yicha:

1-kronshteyn; 2 – bog'lov bolti (o'q) - ishqalanuvchi tebranish so'ngdirgichining valini hisoblashimizda $d_B = 25$ mm; 3 – qo'zg'almas (shayba) disk; disk diametri – $D_d = 160$ mm; qalinligi – 8 mm (ishlab chiqarish vaqtida); 7-8 mm-kapital ta'mirlash vaqtida; 6-8 mm-uz-3; 4 – ishqalanish nakladkalari , nakladkaning diametri – $D_{\phi H} = 120$ mm-rasional kattaliklarni tanlash uchun hisoblashda turlicha 120-140 mm; 5 - harakatlanuvchi disk (burilish richagi) - disk diametri-160 mm; 6 - ishqalanish qopqog'i-uning diametri - 120 mm; qalinligi -12 mm

7- (ishlab chiqarish paytida); 10-12 mm – kapital ta'mirlash paytida; 8-12 mm – JT-3 bosim prujina-prujinaning maksimal siqilishi $h = 67 \pm 0,5$ mm; 8-shayba, 9-maxsus gayka.

Ushbu konstruksiyaning xususiyatlari kamaytirilgan og'irlikning intensivlik funksiyasining tengsizligini keltirib chiqaradi, bu holat bilan taqqoslanganda (1), shaklni olamiz.

Tekshirilayotgan val bo'limlari soni $n=0 \div 3$, $l_{kn} \leq z_n \leq l_{kn+1}$

$$m_B(z) = m_0 \left(1 + \sin \frac{\pi z}{L} \right), \quad (2)$$

bu yerda $m_0 = \frac{\pi d_B^2}{4} \cdot \rho_{CT}$ elastik valning kamaytirilgan og'irligi, kg / m;

$m_{\Delta d} = \frac{\pi(d_d^2 - d_B^2)}{4} \cdot \rho_{CT}$ diskning joylashish zonasida disk tipidagi gidrofriksion so'ndirgich elastik valining kamaytirilgan ekvivalent og'irligi, kg/m; d_d -disklarning diametri, m.

Professor Xromova G.A. va uning shogirdlari rahbarligida ilgari bajarilgan ishlar asosida [4,5,6], YOZ - $y_B(z,t)$ va XOZ - $x_B(z,t)$ ikkita tekislikda o'zgaruvchan qattqlik va og'irlikka ega disk tipidagi gidrofriksion so'ndirgich valining egilish tebranishlari uchun differensial tenglamalar tizimi t shaklida olingan

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial^2 y_B}{\partial t^2} + \frac{E}{m_0 \left(1 + \sin \frac{\pi z}{L} \right)} \cdot \left(-I_{OB} \left(\frac{\pi}{L} \right)^2 \cdot \sin \frac{\pi z}{L} \right) \cdot \frac{\partial^2 y_B}{\partial z^2} + \\ & + \frac{E}{m_0 \left(1 + \sin \frac{\pi z}{L} \right)} I_{OB} \frac{\pi}{L} \cos \frac{\pi z}{L} \cdot \frac{\partial^3 y_B}{\partial z^3} + \\ & + \frac{E}{m_0 \left(1 + \sin \frac{\pi z}{L} \right)} \left(I_{BO} + I_{BO} \cdot \sin \frac{\pi z}{L} \right) \frac{\partial^4 y_B}{\partial z^4} - \\ & - (\omega_B^2 \cdot m_0 - k_{oy}) \cdot y_B + 2\omega_B \frac{\partial x_B}{\partial t} = \frac{p_{oy}(1-\cos(3\omega_B t))}{m_0(1+\sin\frac{\pi z}{L})}. \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial^2 x_B}{\partial t^2} + \frac{E}{m_0 \left(1 + \sin \frac{\pi z}{L} \right)} \cdot \left(-I_{OB} \left(\frac{\pi}{L} \right)^2 \cdot \sin \frac{\pi z}{L} \right) \cdot \frac{\partial^2 x_B}{\partial z^2} + \\ & + \frac{E}{m_0 \left(1 + \sin \frac{\pi z}{L} \right)} I_{OB} \frac{\pi}{L} \cos \frac{\pi z}{L} \cdot \frac{\partial^3 x_B}{\partial z^3} + \\ & + \frac{E}{m_0 \left(1 + \sin \frac{\pi z}{L} \right)} \left(I_{BO} + I_{BO} \cdot \sin \frac{\pi z}{L} \right) \frac{\partial^4 x_B}{\partial z^4} - \\ & - (\omega_B^2 \cdot m_0 - k_{ox}) \cdot x_B + 2\omega_B \frac{\partial y_B}{\partial t} = \frac{p_{ox}(1-\cos(3\omega_B t))}{m_0(1+\sin\frac{\pi z}{L})}. \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

Endi o'zgaruvchan qattqlik va massaga ega bo'lgan valning eguvchi tebranishlari uchun (3) - (4) tenglamalar sistemasini birgalikda yechishga to'g'ri keladi. Biz so'ngdirgich valining butun qismini ($0 \leq z \leq L$) k kesimlar bo'yicha o'zgaruvchi kesimni ajratamiz, $k = 7$, shart bilan $0 \leq z \leq L$, bu yerda L -so'ngdirgich valining umumiy uzunligi

$$A_1(z) = \frac{E \cdot (-I_{OB} \left(\frac{\pi}{L}\right)^2 \cdot \sin \frac{\pi z}{L})}{m_0(1 + \sin \frac{\pi z}{L})}, \quad A_2(z) = \frac{E \cdot I_{OB} \frac{\pi}{L} \cos \frac{\pi z}{L}}{m_0(1 + \sin \frac{\pi z}{L})},$$

$$P_{oy}(z) = \frac{p_{oy}}{m_0(1 + \sin \frac{\pi z}{L})}, \quad A_3(z) = \frac{E}{m_0(1 + \sin \frac{\pi z}{L})} \left(I_{BO} + I_{BO} \cdot \sin \frac{\pi z}{L} \right),$$

$$A_4(z) = \omega_B^2 \cdot m_0 - k_{oy}, \quad B_1(z) = A_1(z), \quad B_2(z) = A_2(z),$$

$$B_3(z) = A_3(z), \quad P_{ox}(z) = \frac{p_{ox}}{m_0(1 + \sin \frac{\pi z}{L})}, \quad B_4(z) = \omega_B^2 \cdot m_0 - k_{ox}.$$

Kiritilgan belgilashlarni hisobga olgan holda disk tipidagi gidrofriksion so'ndirgichlarning elastik valining egilish tebranishlarini differensial tenglamalari tizimi (3) - (4).

$$\frac{\partial^2 y_B}{\partial t^2} + A_1(z) \cdot \frac{\partial^2 y_B}{\partial z^2} + A_2(z) \cdot \frac{\partial^3 y_B}{\partial z^3} + A_3(z) \frac{\partial^4 y_B}{\partial z^4} - A_4 \cdot y_B + 2\omega_B \frac{\partial x_B}{\partial t} = p_{oy}(z) \cdot (1 - \cos(3\omega_B t)), \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 x_B}{\partial t^2} + B_1(z) \cdot \frac{\partial^2 x_B}{\partial z^2} + B_2(z) \cdot \frac{\partial^3 x_B}{\partial z^3} + B_3(z) \frac{\partial^4 x_B}{\partial z^4} - B_4 \cdot x_B + 2\omega_B \frac{\partial y_B}{\partial t} = p_{ox}(z) \cdot (1 - \cos(3\omega_B t)). \quad (6)$$

(5) tenglamalar sistemasini birgalikda yechish bilan ko'pincha (6) o'zgaruvchan qattqlik va massali valning eguvchi tebranishlari uchun biz damper valining butun qismini ajratamiz ($0 \leq z \leq L$) uchastkalarda o'zgaruvchan kesma, uchastkaning ettita bo'lish sharti bilan esa $k = 7$, biz uzunlikdagi o'zgaruvchilar koeffisientlari uchun belgini kiritamiz $0 \leq z \leq L$, bu yerda L - damper valining umumiy uzunligi.

Diskli tebranish so'ngdirgichlarning elastik valining chegara shartlari bilan bog'liq bo'limlari egilish tebranishlarining tabiiy chastotalari tugunlarni mahkamlash shartlariga qarab chastota tenglamalari bilan aniqlanadi [6] iteratsiya usuli bilan. Chegaraviy shartlar bo'yicha bog'lash (siqish) (5) - (6) tenglamalar asosida kompyuter yordamida bo'lakli chiziqli approksimatsiya qilish orqali amalga oshiriladi.

References:

1. Высокоскоростной железнодорожный транспорт. Общий курс: учеб. пособие: в 2 т./ И.П. Киселёв м др.; под ред. И.П. Киселёва.-М.: ФГБОУ «Учебно-методический центр по образованию на железнодорожном транспорте», 2014. Т.2.-372 с.
2. Соколов М.М., Варава В.И., Левит Г.М. Гасители колебаний подвижного состава. Справочник. М.: Транспорт, 1985. - 216 с.
3. Гидравлические и фрикционные гасители колебаний моторвагонного подвижного состава. Руководство по техническому обслуживанию и текущему ремонту. ЦЛПР-

7.2/49-2009. Утверждено распоряжением ОАО «РЖД» от 28 декабря 2009 г. № 2698р, 2009.- 215 с.

4. Khromova G.A., Makhamadalieva M.A. Design scheme of the hydrodynamic friction support of a flexible shaft of a hydrofriction vibration damper used in railway transport // Universum: technical sciences: electron. scientific. journal. 2020. № 7 (76). URL: <https://7universum.com/ru/tech/archive/item/9967>.

5. Khromova G.A., Makhamadalieva M.A., Khromov S.A. Generalized dynamic model of hydrodynamic vibration dampener subject to viscous damping // E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2021. – Т. 264. – С. 05029. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202126405029>

6. Khromova G.A., Kamalov I.S., Makhamadalieva M.A. Improved method of calculating the rational dimensions of parts of hydraulic vibrations dampers of electric trains at high speeds // «Eurasian Journal of Academic Research»: International scientific journal (ISSN: 2181-2020), Volume 2 Issue 12, November 2022, p. 1096-1100. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7386499>